

AUTOMATING THE DIAGNOSIS OF LIVER DISEASE USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

Liver diseases are of significant health concern to the world as they are usually fatal because of delayed diagnosis and ineffective screening. To enhance clinical outcomes, proper and prompt diagnosis is thus important. This paper proposes an automated machine learning-based system of liver disease diagnosis, based on systematic data preprocessing and balancing of classes. To assess a number of machine learning models i.e., LightGBM (LGBM) and Decision Tree (DT), the Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD) of the UCI Machine Learning Repository was utilized. The data was prepared with duplicate removal, filling of missing data using Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE), Z-score normalization for the detection and removal of the outliers. The problem of class imbalance was solved using Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE). According to experimental findings, LGBM model performed best, having accuracy 74.77%, precision 78.72%, recall 67.89% and an F1-score of 72.91%. The results indicate that outliers removal and balanced representation of data is effective in training the machine learning models and subsequent effective prediction of liver disease, as well as in the construction of intelligent decision-support systems in clinical practice.

1 Introduction

Liver disease refers to a wide range of health conditions, including fatty liver disease, viral hepatitis such as hepatitis c, cirrhosis, and liver cancer [1]. Together, these conditions affect millions of people worldwide and are a major cause of illness and death. One of the main reasons for poor outcomes is that liver disease is often detected late, when treatment options are limited and less effective. Current diagnostic methods mainly depend on blood tests, medical imaging such as

ultrasound or CT scans, and in some cases liver biopsy, which is invasive and not suitable for routine screening. As a result, there is a strong need for reliable and non-invasive methods that can support early diagnosis.

In recent years, the growing availability of digital health records, laboratory test results, and clinical datasets has opened new opportunities for the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning (ML) in medical diagnosis [2]. ML techniques have shown promising outcomes in identifying and

classifying diseases such as liver disease [3, 4], Alzheimer's disease [5], and heart disease [6]. Supervised learning models, including decision trees (DT), random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks, have been widely applied to structured medical data and imaging data [7, 8]. Previous studies and surveys highlight the increasing role of ML in liver disease prediction, while also pointing out variations in performance across different models and datasets. Despite these advances, several challenges still limit the clinical usefulness of ML models for liver disease diagnosis. Previously, related studies have utilized small or skewed datasets. In real-life situations, the results of the ML models become less credible when the number of healthy and diseased samples are not equal. Also, the differences in the quality of data, missing values, and inconsistent preprocessing practices complicate the possibility of comparing different studies. The second problem is that the majority of the studies were focused on accuracy without paying much attention to robustness, reproducibility, or use in clinical environment. Prior studies have emphasized the need to manage missing data, manage class imbalance better, select the features with a lot of care, and use appropriate validation to improve the performance of the model and ensure trustworthiness [9].

Solving these problems, our research aims at improving performance of MLMs in diagnosing liver-disease. We focus on effective data preparation, balance representation of classes, and selecting only those features which are of significant importance in terms of the output class. A variety of MLMs are evaluated based on the most common performance evaluation metrics (PEMs) such as accuracy (ac), precision (pr), recall (re) and F1-Score (F1), to ensure fair comparison. We aim to develop a stable, data-driven platform that will assist clinical decision-making and identify liver disease at early stages.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II summarizes the related work in this area while Section III describes the entire work flow of this study. Section IV presents the experimental results and discussion while Section V provides the comparison of this study with the previous studies

and demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach. Section VI concludes the study with directions for future research.

2 Related Work

ML has increasingly been used in healthcare to support the early detection of liver diseases by uncovering patterns in clinical data that are difficult to identify through traditional analysis alone. Recent research has demonstrated that estimating and preprocessing data along with the choice of selected features can significantly improve the quality of the diagnostic task. For example, earlier work using the Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD) demonstrated that applying feature selection before classification improves prediction accuracy across commonly used models such as logistic regression, random forest, and support vector machines [10]. The findings demonstrated the importance feature selection in diagnosing liver disease through ML.

A number of studies have discussed the performance of various ML algorithms in predicting liver disease. Comparative studies involving models such as logistic regression, DT, k-nearest neighbors, boosting methods, and support vector machines have reported that ensemble-based approaches often achieve better performance [11]. Specifically, random forest and boosting algorithms have been demonstrated to be able to better manage the complex relationship between biochemical features compared to individual classifiers. These models benefit from combining multiple decision rules, which helps reduce errors and improve robustness.

One major research direction that has been addressed in several medical studies previously is addressing the class imbalance problem where the number of patients and healthy individuals are unevenly distributed. Studies that applied data balancing techniques such as the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), combined with cross-validation strategies, reported noticeable improvements in prediction stability and overall performance. Ensemble voting classifiers, when used alongside balanced data, have also demonstrated stronger results compared to individual models [12].

In addition to predicting general liver diseases, there are studies that have focused on individual diseases like non-alcoholic fatty liver disease using a combination of biochemical and physical markers [13]. These works concluded that support vector machines tend to have reliable and consistent performance on various combinations of features, and thus, they are useful in the real-life situation of clinical screening. Other researchers have explored hybrid approaches by combining boosting algorithms with traditional DT models and tuning their parameters, which resulted in moderate but meaningful gains in diagnostic accuracy [14].

Other comparative studies have affirmed that models like random forest, LightGBM (LGBM), and gradient boosting are effective in the sense that their performance highly relies on the appropriate feature engineering and preprocessing [9]. There are also instances where instance-based, such as k-nearest neighbor, approaches delivered competitive results following tuning of the features and this indicates that local patterns of data would also be applicable in the biomedical prediction tasks [15]. Margin-based classifiers such as support vector machines have repeatedly shown stable performance, particularly when working with limited or heterogeneous datasets.

In general, currently available literature demonstrates that the quality of preprocessing, feature selection, and data balancing is crucial in the diagnosis of liver disease with the help of ML. Ensemble learning methods generally outperform single classifiers, but most reported accuracies remain in a moderate range, and many approaches lack consistency across different datasets. Furthermore, limited attention has been given to building models that are both reliable and suitable for clinical use. Motivated by these gaps, the present study focuses on improving diagnostic performance by combining effective preprocessing, balanced data handling, and robust ML models to support more accurate and dependable liver disease diagnosis.

3 Methodology

The methodological approach employed in this study was structured to improve both the accuracy and robustness of ML models for liver disease

detection. The overall framework comprised several sequential stages, including data acquisition, preprocessing, class balancing, model development, and hyperparameter tuning. Each stage was implemented with careful consideration to ensure strong generalization across heterogeneous clinical data while reducing the impact of bias arising from data irregularities.

3.1 Dataset Collection

The experimental analysis was conducted using the Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD), sourced from the UCI Machine Learning Repository [16], a widely recognized open-access resource for evaluating predictive modeling techniques. The dataset contains 583 samples described by 10 attributes associated with liver function. These include biochemical indicators such as Total Bilirubin, Direct Bilirubin, Alkaline Phosphatase (AlkPhos), Serum Glutamic-Pyruvic Transaminase (SGPT), Serum Glutamic-Oxaloacetic Transaminase (SGOT), Total Proteins, Albumin, and the Albumin-to-Globulin (A/G) ratio. In addition, demographic variables such as Age and Gender are provided. The class label specifies whether an individual is diagnosed with liver disease (class 1) or is healthy (class 2).

A notable characteristic of the dataset is its class imbalance, where records corresponding to liver disease patients significantly exceed those of healthy individuals. This imbalance posed a risk of biased model learning, thereby necessitating the application of appropriate preprocessing and data balancing strategies prior to model training.

3.2 Dataset Preprocessing

Data preprocessing plays a vital role in ensuring the quality and consistency of input features for ML algorithms. In this study, preprocessing involved the elimination of duplicate records, handling of missing values, encoding of categorical variables, feature scaling, and identification of outliers.

3.2.1 Removal of Duplicate Records

An initial examination of the ILPD dataset identified 13 duplicated entries. Such redundancies can introduce bias and artificially enhance model performance during training.

Duplicate records were detected through systematic record comparison and subsequently removed, retaining only unique observations. This step helped preserve data authenticity and reduced the likelihood of overfitting caused by repeated data patterns.

3.2.2 Handling of Missing Values

Ensuring data completeness is essential for effective ML model training. In the ILPD dataset, missing entries were identified in the Albumin-to-Globulin (A/G) ratio feature, a clinically important indicator of liver function. To address this issue, the Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) technique was applied. This method has been widely adopted in prior research for handling missing data [17, 18]. MICE works by iteratively estimating missing values for each variable using regression models based on the remaining features, thereby retaining inter-feature dependencies. Compared to simpler strategies such as mean or median imputation, this approach more effectively preserves data variability and multivariate relationships, which are particularly important in medical diagnostic applications.

3.2.3 Encoding of Categorical Variables

Most ML models operate exclusively on numerical data. Consequently, the categorical attribute Gender, originally represented as “Male” and “Female,” was transformed into a binary numerical format, with Male encoded as 1 and Female as 0. This straightforward encoding scheme maintains clarity and interpretability while enabling algorithms such as logistic regression, random forest, and support vector machines to process the feature efficiently.

3.2.4 Z-Score Standardization

The dataset comprised features expressed in varying units and ranges, including biochemical enzyme measurements and demographic information such as age. To prevent attributes with larger numerical values from dominating the learning process, Z-score standardization was applied to all continuous variables, with the exception of the binary Gender feature. This scaling technique transforms each feature by centering it around zero and normalizing

its spread to a standard deviation of one, thereby placing all variables on a comparable scale. Applying Z-score normalization is especially important for algorithms that rely on distance calculations or decision margins, such as k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM), as it promotes faster model convergence and ensures that no single feature exerts undue influence due to its magnitude.

3.2.5 Outlier Treatment

Outliers can adversely affect model performance, especially in healthcare datasets where extreme values may arise from measurement variability rather than true pathological conditions. To identify anomalous observations, a statistical criterion of ± 3 standard deviations from the mean was applied to each numerical feature. Data points falling outside this range were considered potential outliers and removed from the dataset. This step helped enhance model stability and robustness. Following the removal of anomalous records, the newly introduced missing values were re-estimated using the MICE imputation technique to preserve the integrity and completeness of the dataset. This sequential strategy ensured that data inconsistencies were thoroughly addressed before proceeding with the model training phase.

3.3 Dataset Balancing

Class imbalance poses a significant challenge in classification tasks, as learning algorithms tend to prioritize the dominant class and consequently exhibit reduced performance on underrepresented samples, which in this study correspond to healthy individuals. To mitigate this issue, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was employed, in line with its proven effectiveness in previous medical classification studies [19, 20]. SMOTE compensates for imbalance by generating new minority-class samples through interpolation between existing observations, leading to a more evenly distributed dataset. Compared to simple random oversampling, this strategy minimizes the likelihood of overfitting and preserves the intrinsic structure of the minority class in the feature space. As a result of applying SMOTE, the dataset attained a near-equal distribution between liver

disease and non-disease instances, enabling fairer model training and more dependable evaluation outcomes.

3.4 Machine Learning Models Employed

Two supervised learning techniques were selected for this study based on their proven success in biomedical classification tasks: LGBM and DT. These models provide complementary strengths, allowing for a thorough comparative analysis of predictive performance.

3.4.1 Light Gradient Boosting Machine

LGBM is an advanced ensemble learning algorithm based on gradient boosting DT. It builds models in a sequential manner, where each new tree focuses on correcting the errors made by previous ones. One of its key strengths lies in its efficiency and scalability, achieved through techniques such as histogram-based feature binning and leaf-wise tree growth. These characteristics allow LGBM to handle high-dimensional data and complex nonlinear relationships effectively while maintaining fast training speed. In medical diagnosis tasks, such as liver disease prediction, LGBM is particularly valuable due to its ability to capture subtle interactions among clinical features and deliver high predictive accuracy with reduced computational cost.

3.4.2 Decision Tree

The Decision Tree classifier is a simple yet powerful supervised learning method that models decisions in a hierarchical, tree-like structure. It recursively splits the dataset based on feature values that

maximize class separation, leading to easily interpretable decision rules. This transparency makes DT especially suitable for healthcare applications, where model interpretability is essential for clinical trust and decision support. Although DT may be prone to overfitting when used alone, they provide a strong baseline model and offer clear insights into feature importance and decision pathways, facilitating a better understanding of the underlying data patterns.

Together, these two models offer complementary perspectives: LGBM emphasizes predictive strength and efficiency, while the DT prioritizes interpretability and simplicity. This combination enables a balanced and meaningful evaluation of ML approaches for liver disease classification.

4 Results and Discussion

This section analyzes the experimental findings obtained from the implemented ML models and provides a critical comparison of their effectiveness in liver disease classification using the Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD). The discussion focuses on how systematic preprocessing, dataset balancing, and hyperparameter tuning influenced the overall predictive capability of the models, as reflected through accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

Model performance was assessed using four widely adopted evaluation measures: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score [21]. These metrics collectively provide a balanced assessment by considering not only overall correctness but also the model's ability to correctly identify liver disease cases and avoid misclassification of healthy individuals.

Figure 1: Performance Evaluation Metrics of DT for Liver Disease Diagnosis.

Figure 2: Performance Evaluation Metrics of LGBM for Liver Disease Diagnosis.

Figure 1 presents bar graphs illustrating the performance of the DT model across the selected metrics, while Figure 2 depicts the corresponding results for the LGBM. The DT achieved an accuracy of 67.89%, with precision, recall, and F1-score values of 69.70%, 63.30%, and 66.35%, respectively. These results indicate that while DT demonstrates reasonable classification capability, its relatively lower recall suggests a tendency to miss a notable proportion of liver disease cases. This limitation can be attributed to the model's inherent sensitivity to data variability and its tendency to overfit despite preprocessing and balancing efforts. In contrast, LGBM consistently outperformed the DT across all evaluation metrics, as clearly

visualized in Figure 2. The LGBM model achieved an accuracy of 74.77%, alongside substantially higher precision (78.72%) and recall (67.89%), resulting in an F1-score of 72.91%. The improved recall indicates a stronger ability to correctly identify liver disease patients, which is a critical requirement in medical diagnostic systems where false negatives can have serious clinical consequences. The superior performance of LGBM can be attributed to its ensemble-based learning strategy, which effectively captures complex nonlinear relationships and feature interactions present in clinical data.

Figure 3: Comparison between DT and LGBM for liver disease diagnosis.

The comparative results shown in the radar graph of Figure 3 highlight the importance of advanced ensemble methods for medical classification tasks involving heterogeneous and imbalanced datasets. While the DT offers interpretability and simplicity, its lower predictive performance limits its standalone applicability in high-stakes diagnostic settings. LGBM, on the other hand, benefits significantly from preprocessing steps, SMOTE-based class balancing, and optimized hyperparameters, enabling it to generalize more effectively across diverse samples.

Overall, the bar graph comparisons in Figures 1 and 2 reinforce that LGBM provides a more reliable and clinically relevant prediction framework for liver disease detection compared to the DT. These findings underscore the value of combining robust preprocessing pipelines with powerful ensemble learning techniques to enhance diagnostic accuracy and decision support in healthcare applications.

5 Conclusion

This study proposed a systematic machine learning-driven approach for liver disease prediction using the Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD), incorporating comprehensive preprocessing, missing value imputation, outlier removal, class balancing, and model optimization to ensure robust and unbiased learning. The use of MICE and SMOTE significantly enhanced data quality and addressed inherent dataset limitations, enabling reliable model evaluation. A comparative assessment of DT and LGBM models revealed that while the DT offered reasonable performance and interpretability, it struggled to consistently identify all disease cases. In contrast, LGBM demonstrated superior accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, highlighting its effectiveness in capturing complex clinical patterns and reducing diagnostic errors. These findings emphasize the importance of combining advanced preprocessing strategies with ensemble learning techniques to improve predictive accuracy in medical diagnosis, and they suggest that LGBM has strong potential as a practical decision-support tool for early liver disease detection in clinical settings.

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